

ELIXIR Commissioned Service: Training Platform 2024-2026 Work Plan

Sections in the Training SPLASH with the data from the TtT Instructors and TtT course feedback and assessments

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the integration of ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer (TtT) content into the SPLASH platform, in line with the objectives of the [ELIXIR Training Platform's work plan](#). The content was extended, thereby enhancing the value and usability of SPLASH as a central access point for training-related materials.

The result is publicly accessible at:

<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/train-the-trainer>

The implementation is reflected in the updated platform content and the associated development work, which has been documented through the relevant milestones (M3.1 and M3.4) and a corresponding [Pull Request](#). These references collectively describe the scope and completion of the deliverable.

This contribution supports the strategic goal of consolidating and maintaining sustainable training infrastructure within ELIXIR.

Document info

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

TtT	ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer
SPLASH	Skills, Professional development, Learning Assessment, Support and Help

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Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable was to improve accessibility and visibility of Train-the-Trainer (TtT) resources by incorporating them into SPLASH, ELIXIR's central platform for training assets. TtT resources are foundational to building capacity and supporting new trainers across ELIXIR Nodes.

Description of Work

Objectives

The primary objective was to integrate and present existing TtT resources within SPLASH in a coherent and accessible manner. Specific goals included:

- Designing a page structure suited to TtT content
- Ensuring consistency with SPLASH visual and content standards
- Linking to guiding information to engage in multiple ways with the community

Implementation

The TtT page was created using the existing SPLASH codebase and follows the site's static-site architecture based on GitHub Pages. The page includes:

- A summary of the TtT programme and its goals
- Links to ELIXIR TtT events and key documentation
- Descriptions of pedagogical focus areas
- Presentation of community members and guide to who is available to teach each session

The implementation was delivered via Pull Request and reviewed collaboratively. Relevant references to this work are included in Milestone M3.1 and M3.4. An issue ([#149](#)) linked to compatibility between the contributors metadata field in SPLASH and the useful data on this page was opened. Further updates will follow developments on this topic.

Results

The final TtT page is available at:

<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/train-the-trainer>

The content is structured for both new and experienced trainers and presents the following sections:

- Introduction to TtT
- Testimonials and relevant resources
- Information on trainers network
- TtT learning objectives and core aims of the course

- Information on upcoming ELIXIR TtT events (through the TeSS widget)

Dissemination Plans

The TtT section is publicly available via the SPLASH platform:

<https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/train-the-trainer>

The work was conducted via a version-controlled development process with documentation included in the project's milestones. No further standalone publication is currently planned, as the content is fully accessible via the platform.